

WEAI

Women's Empowerment Agriculture Index 2023

Instruction for the enumerators

Linking East and West African farming systems experience into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Agriculture urbaine et promotion d'une alimentation saine et locale pour le développement d'un système agroalimentaire durable et inclusif
AID 012590/01/1

WEAI

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1. Women's Empowerment Agriculture Index

The *Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index* (WEAI) is a survey-based tool codeveloped by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), the Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI), and the U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) that directly measure women's empowerment and inclusion in the agricultural sector through a standardized procedure. The WEAI builds on research to develop indicators of agency and empowerment that propose domain-specific measures of empowerment obtained using questions that can be fielded in individual or household surveys. The questionnaire modules drew on past surveys developed by IFPRI, Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), and the Gender Asset Gap Project to develop modules on agricultural decision-making, assets, credit, and income, as well as OPHI questions related to relative autonomy. Following the test of an earlier version of the survey, the WEAI teams from IFPRI and USAID, in consultation with OPHI, undertook an extensive process of revising the WEAI to clarify the questions that had proved challenging in the field while at the same time maintaining cross-cultural applicability. Following this process, they elaborated a shorter, streamlined version known as the Abbreviated WEAI (A-WEAI).

Acra has already used a first version of the WEAI in 2018, when IFPRI was developing the abridged version to facilitate the task of NGOs who must carry out rapid surveys and gave us a temporary model. The current version of the abbreviated WEAI differs with regard to the order and wording of the questions, as well as the question on the ability to speak in public, which has been eliminated in the updated version of the questionnaire. For all other aspects, the structure of the questionnaire is the same.

The A-WEAI questionnaire will elicit information on five domains of empowerment:

- **Production:** Women and men's sole or joint decision-making over food and cash-crop farming, livestock, and fisheries.
- **Resources:** Women and men's ownership of and decision-making power over productive resources such as land, livestock, agricultural equipment, consumer durables, and credit.
- **Income:** Women and men's sole or joint control over income and expenditures.
- **Leadership:** Women and men's membership in economic or social groups.
- **Time:** Women and men's allocation of time to productive and domestic tasks.

2. Who should be interviewed ?

The target of the survey are the “households” living in rural context. A household is a group of people who live together and take food from the “same pot.” We consider a household member someone who has lived in the household at least 6 months, and at least half of the week in each week in those months. If someone stays in the same household but does not bear any costs for food or does not take food from the same pot, they are not considered household members. For each household, we will interview a «**primary**» and a «**secondary**» respondent.

The **primary respondents** are those which are self-identified as the primary members responsible for the decision making, both social and economic decisions related to agriculture, within the household.

The **secondary respondents** are members of the household who are not the main decision makers within it. The questionnaire needs to be administered to a primary and a secondary respondent and, if the primary respondent is a man, the secondary respondent must be a woman. However, if the primary respondent is a woman, there is no need to interview a secondary respondent.

- The primary and secondary respondents are usually husband and wife; however, they can also be another member as long as there is one male and one female aged 18 and over (for instance a mother could be living with her adult son or father with an adult daughter).
- In general, the primary decision maker is also the head of household, but this may not always be the case (i.e. elderly parent living with adult son/daughter and the adult son/daughter may be the primary or secondary respondent).
- It may also be the case that there is only a primary female respondent and there is no adult male present in the household. In cases whereby the primary male adult is absent from the household due to male migration (has gone for work) and has been or is expected to be away for more than 3 months out of the next/previous 6 months, the primary female adult is considered the primary decision maker.

- In cases where there is only a primary male and no female, do not interview the household; there must be a primary or secondary female in the household to administer the WEAI.

We must also consider the crucial problem of the **confidentiality** of interviews. Before starting the interview, interviewers should assure respondents that the information collected will be kept strictly confidential. It should be noted that, to protect the confidentiality of respondents and their responses, all sensitive information (e.g., respondent identification) will be hidden and removed from publicly available datasets. To this end, a document has been drawn up **to obtain the informed consent of the interviewee**, to be signed by the interviewee when possible or to be signed by the interviewer after having obtained verbal consent.

Questions should be asked exactly as they are worded; avoid changing words or phrases, adding or deleting words to a question. In addition, unless it is a jump diagram, a question must always be asked, even when the answer is obvious to the interviewer: it is necessary to avoid at all costs writing an answer without asking the question.

This questionnaire must be administered separately to individuals as the primary and secondary respondents. We strongly recommend that enumerators travel in male and female pairs and carry duplicate copies of the A-WEAI module. This facilitates interviewing the primary male and female decision-maker separately and in private. Before starting the interview, please double check to ensure:

- You have gained informed consent for the individual in the household questionnaire.
- You have sought to interview the individual in private or where other members of the household cannot overhear or contribute answers.
- Do not attempt to make responses between the primary and secondary respondent the same it is ok for them to be different.

3. The questions of the survey

The survey on your tablet is structured in five modules:

- Section G1 covers the identification of the individuals involved in the research.
- Section G2 is based on the question about decision-making in production.
- Section G3 is divided into two sub-sections: G3 (A) focuses on the productive capital while G3 (B) focuses on credit.
- Section G4 is exclusively about the use of the time.
- Section G5 about group membership.

Remember that you always asking the question referring to the individual that is talking to you. In languages where there is a singular you and a plural you, the questions refer to the singular you (the person being interviewed, not the respondent together with his or her family). If the local language does not distinguish between singular or plural, make sure the respondent understands that this applies to just him/her.

MODULE G1 : Individual identification

You should insert a code to identify each household and each respondent. G1.01 gives a numeric code for the household after the initial of your country (ex. GHA 01, BUR 01, KEN 01, please check on the document "WEAI Code" shared with you), while for the individual respondent (G1.02) always give "01" for first respondent and "02" for second respondent. Do not put any personal data on the survey, you should only collect them on the consent forms. G1.03 is about the sex of the respondent, G1.04 about the type of household, G1.06 asks if it was possible to administer the questionnaire alone (which is the best option), you will find G1.05 at the very end of the survey to check if the interview was fully completed.

MODULE G2 : Role in household decision-making around production and income generation

The purpose of this module is to get an idea about men's and women's relative roles in decision-making around income-generating activities. Do not attempt to ensure that responses are the same between the male and female respondent. It is okay for them to be different.

This module includes the following questions:

G2.01: Did you (singular) yourself participate in [ACTIVITY] in the past 12 months (that is within the last [one/two] cropping seasons), from [PRESENT MONTH] last year to [PRESENT MONTH] this year? (YES/NO) This question will be repeated for 6 activities, if the answer is YES it will move to the following questions.

Please note the following:

- The reference time frame for this question is always 12 months. In some cases, for crop production related activities, it will be helpful to ask the respondent to think about the last two cropping seasons if the area has a bi-annual crop season. In other cases, the reference period should only be one cropping season depending on the number of cropping seasons per year, the intervention and the timing between surveys. For this specific survey, however, we are asking about the last 12 months.
- If the respondent answers "no" he/she did not participate for the activity, the survey will automatically skip to the next activity.

G2.02 : When decisions are made regarding the following aspects of household life, who normally makes the decision?

You can answer all applicable categories from the following:

- Self 01
- Spouse 02
- Other HH member 03
- Other non-HH member 04
- Not applicable 98 -> If this code is selected the survey will automatically skip to the next activity.

G2.03 : How much input did you (singular) have in making decisions about [ACTIVITY]?

Enter the appropriate response from the list (only one answer):

- No input or input in few decisions 01
- Input into some decisions 02
- Input into most or all decisions 03
- No decision made 98

G2.04 : To what extent do you feel you can make your own personal decisions regarding this [ACTIVITY] if you want(ed) to?

One response only from the following categories:

- Not at all 01
- Small extent 02
- Medium extent 03
- To a high extent 04

G2.05 : How much input did you (singular) have in decisions on the use of income generated from [ACTIVITY]?

Choose a single answer from the list:

- No input or input in few decisions 01
- Input into some decisions 02
- Input into most or all decisions 03
- No decision made 98

Regarding G2.03/G2.05, please note the following:

The answer "not applicable" should be entered only in the case that the decision is not made, for example crops may have been lost so no income was generated or livestock/livestock products were not sold so income was not generated. In some cases, respondents will need more explanation about what certain categories contain. In this case the enumerator can use simple examples to explain. Examples can be tailored to the specific activities undertaken by households in the survey area. Here are some examples which can be used:

- Food crop farming: crops that are grown primarily for household food consumption: For example, did you have input into decisions about what crops to plant this year or in which plots they would be planted, or which seeds, fertilizer (other inputs) your family would buy?
- Cash crop farming: crops that are grown primary for sale in the market. For example, did you have input into decisions about how much of your family's land would be used for growing cash crops, or about the crops to be grown for sale, and the inputs to be used for those crops?
- Livestock raising: for example, did you have input into decisions about the purchase, care, or sale of livestock?
- Non-farm economic activities: small business, self-employment, buy-and-sell. For example, did you have input into purchases made for a small business or goods sold?
- Wage and salary employment: in-kind or monetary work both agriculture and other wage work. For example, did you have input into decisions about whether you or other household members will work outside the home?
- Fishing or fishpond culture: for example, did you have input into decisions about when to fish, how to stock a fishpond, or inputs for fish culture?

- Major household expenditures: for example, did you have input into purchases of large appliances for the house like a refrigerator or furniture? Or large assets such as land or a bicycle?
- Minor household expenditures: or example, did you have input into lesser household expenditures, such as those for daily needs, like food consumption?

For the activities, "major household expenditure" and "minor household expenditure" questions G2.01 and G2.05 will not be asked, but the survey will begin with G2.02.

In the case that a crop is grown partially for food and partially for sale on the market, record that activity only once, in the category which the crop is primarily grown for (in terms of volume).

MODULE G3 (A) : Access to productive capital

The purpose of this module is to get an idea about men's and women's access to capital or assets and their ability to control use of the resource. Again, do not attempt to ensure that responses are the same between the male and female respondent. It is okay for them to be different. The questions ask about men's and women's access to different types of assets (14 types of assets). These are the questions:

G3.01: Does anyone in your household currently have any [ITEM]? (YES/NO) The question will be repeated for 14 items, if the answer is YES it will move to the following question.

G3.02: Do you own any of the [ITEM]?

Answers: YES SOLELY, YES JOINTLY, NO, you can choose several answers, for example if the person you are interviewing has access to a private plot and a community plot of land at the same time and other similar situations.

- Examples of each asset type should be adapted to each country/context. Examples given in parentheses for some of the asset categories are merely suggestions and not intended to be a comprehensive list. When making examples, it is important to consider all categories. For instance, while a bicycle is a "large consumer durable", there is a "transport" category so it should fall under that; do not double count assets.
- It is important not to double count assets into two categories when thinking about different asset categories.
- Agricultural land (pieces/plots) includes both agricultural land used for growing crops as well as land used for livestock. It may include land that is owned, borrowed, rented or leased.
- Non-farm business equipment includes any asset used for small businesses including solar panels (if used for recharging), sewing machine, brewing equipment, chapatti fryers... The distinguishing factor from farm equipment (which includes equipment for growing food) is that value must be added to the production (i.e. brewing or processing like baking bread etc.).

- You should count the asset in G3.01 even if it is not functioning at the time of the interview as long as there is a resale value for the asset (i.e. it can be fixed or it can be sold to buy another productive asset or service).

In addition, please note the following specific instructions:

Note that question G3.01 means HAVE, as in “have access to” or own, rent or lease, whereas question G3.02 is about OWNING only.

MODULE G3 (B): Access to credit

This module contains questions on access to credit. G3.04 ask if any member of the household got any loan – in cash, in kind or a mix of both – in the last 12 months; the question will be repeated for 7 lending sources. If the answer is yes, G3.05 asks who decided the sources of the loan and G3.06 asks who decided how to use the borrowed money. The options are:

- Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)
- Formal lender (bank/financial institution)
- Informal lender (person who lends money outside recognized institutions and outside family or friendly circles)
- Friends or relatives
- Microfinance or group lending (village savings and loan associations, other local/ community microfinance groups)
- Informal credit/savings groups such as carousels, tontines, funeral societies, etc.

A few things to consider:

- Lending sources can be adapted to the country context; however, it is important that they are distinguished from each other and there is no double counting. The same credit source should never be counted in more than one category. If you feel that what the respondent is describing could fall into two or more categories, use your judgement and place it in the category that seems most appropriate.
- The recall timeframe is within the last year; however, if a credit source has been ongoing for more than 1 year (i.e. a multi-year loan that began 2 years ago) it should be counted.
- “In-kind” refers to credit given in the form of goods, commodities or services as opposed to cash.
- “Informal lenders” refers to those like moneylenders or others that are NOT included in one of the other categories of credit.
- In the case of G3.04, in some cases the individual may not know if other members of the household have accessed or used a specific type of credit, and in this case the response 97 “Don’t know” can be entered.
- For G3.05 and G3.06 circle all applicable answers; make sure to probe the respondent and ask “is there anybody else?”.

MODULE G4: Time allocation

The purpose of this module is to get an idea about how men's and women's time is spent. Types of activities and their duration can be used in economic as well as in social analysis, e.g. women's contribution in economic activities; the value of home production and the informal sector; productivity; time poverty and others.

G4.01 : Please records the hours spent on each of the following activities for the individual in the last complete 24 hours.

Activity	Specification
Sleeping and resting	Includes resting, e.g. trying to sleep.
Eating and drinking	Includes drinking and eating at restaurants and with friends. But eating just snacks with friends or when watching TV is not regarded as the main activity..
Personal care	May include bathing, getting dressed, brushing teeth/hair, etc. Record purchased services like haircutting as "shopping/getting service".
School	Personal care and shorter breaks during school hours are treated as school.
Work as employed	Includes personal care, eating, traveling, reading, etc. during the working hours which are part of your income generating activities (i.e. you are sent across town to attend a meeting, or you are reading for work purposes) but excludes commuting to and from work (record under "traveling and commuting").
Own business work	Includes own account work and household related businesses, except farming, fishing and textile work even for selling.
Farming/livestock/ fishing	Includes small-scale food production in the garden for own consumption and selling. Includes fishing for own consumption and selling but excludes fishing just for fun (record as "social activities and hobbies").
Shopping/getting service (including health services)	Includes paid personal care, like haircutting, visit to the doctor or health facility (obtaining health services), car servicing and banking, etc. Any traveling linked to shopping will be noted as travels.

Activité	Spécifications
Weaving, sewing, textile care	Includes textile work for selling and own consumption but excludes repairing of textiles (note as “domestic work”).
Cooking	Includes time spent getting food at market (but not transport time, which is counted under transport), preparing food to cook, time cooking, and cleaning up. Does not include time spent harvesting crops (include in “farming/livestock/fishing”).
Domestic work	Includes all unpaid domestic work such as fetching water and firewood, cleaning, washing clothes and other household chores (excluding cooking). Paid domestic work is counted as “work as employed.”.
Care for children/adults elderly	Includes unpaid care for all persons at home as well as outside home. Paid care is counted as “work as employed.”.
Traveling and Commuting	Travels to and from work or school. Travel includes all travels, except commuting and travels on working hours. Includes walking if the purpose is not exercising. Longer journeys will be separated by activities like eating, personal care, etc.
Watching TV/listening to the radio/reading	Is often a second activity, particularly outside home, but comes first if just eating snacks or drinking at the same time. Includes all kind of reading, except homework for school and reading at work.
Exercising	All kind of physical sport activities including walking, if the purpose is not moving from one place to another (which is counted as “traveling and commuting”).
Social activities and hobbies	This category captures any social activities, such as sitting with family, visiting friends, talking on the phone with friends, visiting a drinking spot with friends, going to watch sporting activities etc. This category also encompasses conjugal activities if they are not for paid work (otherwise can be captured as “work as employed” or “own business”). Also includes gardening, fishing and other production activities if they are just for fun.
Religious activities	Include attending services, praying or other religious activities/ceremonies. Note that if the individual is a Pastor, Imam or other person that does this activity as their occupation/work, it should be counted in the “work as employed” category and not as a religious activity.

	Day		Evening	Night								
	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00	20:00	21:00	22:00	23:00	24:00	1:00	2:00	3:00
<i>Sleeping and resting</i>												
<i>Eating and drinking</i>												
<i>Personal care</i>												
<i>School</i>												
<i>Work as employed</i>												
<i>Own business work</i>												
<i>Farming/livestock/ fishing</i>												
<i>Shopping/getting service (including health services)</i>												
<i>Weaving, sewing, textile care</i>												
<i>Cooking</i>												
<i>Domestic work</i>												
<i>Care for children/ adults elderly</i>												
<i>Traveling and Commuting</i>												
<i>Watching TV/ listening to the radio/reading</i>												
<i>Exercising</i>												
<i>Social activities and hobbies</i>												
<i>Religious activities</i>												
<i>Care for children/ adults elderly</i>												

You should never have more than one activity marked for a time period. If the respondent was doing multiple things (for instance eating breakfast and listening to the radio) determine which activity is primary and mark that category for the time. In this case, if eating is the primary activity, it should be marked for the time period.

- When a respondent describes many activities in a short period, such as their morning routine, use your best judgement to figure out which categories the majorities of activities belong in and fill that time grid for the period.

- It is most helpful to fill this table as a conversation with the respondent, rather than asking them what they were doing at 4:15, 4:30, 4:45 and so on. First, it is helpful to establish what time the respondent woke up and went to bed, in order to keep only the waking hours. Then, ask the respondent what they did after they woke up and fill in the rest of the day. For example, ask after you got up what did you do? Or, work by filling in other time markers (i.e. always take lunch at 1, prayer time, etc.)
- You must be sure that the total hours you indicated in the survey is 24.

G4.02 : In the last 24 hours did you work (at home or outside the home) more than usual, about the same as usual, or less than usual ?

For this question, we want to know how the respondent's previous day compared to their usual routine.

MODULE G5 : Group membership

The purpose of this module is to get information regarding men's and women's access to social capital. There are two questions for this module:

G5.01 : Is there a [GROUP] in your community? (YES/NO) This question will be repeated for 10 types of groups:

- Agriculture/livestock/fishery producer groups (including marketing groups)
- Water users group
- Forest user group
- Credit or microfinance group (including SACCOs/merry-go-rounds/ VSLAs)
- Mutuals help or insurance groups (including burial societies)
- Trade and business association groups
- Civic groups (improving community) or charitable organizations (helping others)
- Religious groups
- Other groups (only if they do not fit into any other category)
- Other (specify)

The answer YES leads to the following question.

G5.02 : Are you an active member of this [GROUP]? (YES/NO)

- Note that groups in the community can be either formal or informal and customary groups.
- Note that being an “active” member of a group should be defined by the respondent (i.e. his/her subjective idea of what being a member constitutes). If asked by the respondent, you may indicate that “active” membership could constitute attending meetings, paying a user fee, holding a leadership position within the group, etc. However, explain that there is too much variation in group type to have a standard definition for an active member so encourage the respondent to use his/her own judgment. Note that “community” is left to the respondent to define and may be groups within his/her own village or encompass a larger geographic range including a nearby village or city.
- Note that many groups have multiple activities. For instance, an agricultural group may have a microfinance component. When this is the case, choose the group category that represents the primary activity. If the agricultural group provides many extension services, including microfinance, then agricultural group, not credit or microfinance group, should be selected. Ask the respondent to describe the group in greater detail if you are unclear.
- A “religious group” may include going to church, the mosque, etc. or being a member of a small prayer or religious discussion group.
- If a certain group is not contextually appropriate, it may be replaced with the appropriate group in the same category; if no replacement exists it may be omitted from the questionnaire. Whether or not to omit a group should be decided during the training; a group should never be omitted when conducting a questionnaire.

At the end of the interview, thank the respondent, then fill up the question on the outcome of the interview (G1.05).

4. When to do the survey?

In the case of ACRA projects, the purpose of the surveys is to assess the impact of different project activities in women's empowerment. It is therefore necessary to plan two surveys: a first survey before the start of activities, to have an initial baseline; and a second survey, to be arranged after completing at least one complete agricultural cycle since the start of project activities.

It is important that the baseline and endline surveys be conducted in the same period, so that the data is comparable; and that the final survey be conducted after the implementation of all project innovations in the agricultural cycle, so that any impacts (positive or negative) are already visible.

Both surveys (initial and final) should be followed by qualitative reflection among the researcher and interviewers to understand the dynamics and hierarchies behind the data and formulate hypotheses and explanations about the data collected.

MODULE G. WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT IN AGRICULTURE INDEX – A-WEAI Version

Note: the information in module G1 can be captured in different ways; however there must be a way to a) identify the proper individual within the household to be asked the survey, b) link this individual from the module to the household roster, c) code the outcome of the interview, especially if the individual is not available, to distinguish this from missing data, d) record who else in the household was present during the interview. This instrument must be adapted for country context including translations into local languages when appropriate.

Enumerator: *This questionnaire should be administered separately to the primary and secondary respondents identified in the household roster (Section B) of the household level questionnaire. You should complete this coversheet for each individual identified in the "selection section" even if the individual is not available to be interviewed for reporting purposes.*

Please double check to ensure:

- You have completed the roster section of the household questionnaire to identify the correct primary and/or secondary respondent(s);
- You have noted the household ID and individual ID correctly for the person you are about to interview;
- You have gained informed consent for the individual in the household questionnaire;
- You have sought to interview the individual in private or where other members of the household cannot overhear or contribute answers.
- Do not attempt to make responses between the primary male decisionmaker and the primary female decisionmaker the same—it is ok for them to be different.

MODULE G1. INDIVIDUAL IDENTIFICATION

	Code		Code						
G1.01. HOUSEHOLD IDENTIFICATION:	<table border="1" style="width: 100px; height: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table>							G1.05. OUTCOME OF INTERVIEW:	COMPLETED1 HOUSEHOLD MEMBER TOO ILL TO RESPOND/COGNITIVELY IMPAIRED2 RESPONDENT NOT AT HOME/TEMPORARILY UNAVAILABLE...3 RESPONDENT NOT AT HOME/EXTENDED ABSENCE.....4 REFUSED5 COULD NOT LOCATE6
G1.02. NAME OF RESPONDENT CURRENTLY BEING INTERVIEWED (ID CODE FROM ROSTER IN SECTION B HOUSEHOLD ROSTER): SURNAME, OTHER NAME NAME: _____	<table border="1" style="width: 60px; height: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 30px; height: 20px;"></td> <td style="width: 30px; height: 20px;"></td> </tr> </table>			G1.06. ABILITY TO BE INTERVIEWED ALONE:	ALONE1 WITH ADULT FEMALES PRESENT2 WITH ADULT MALES PRESENT3 WITH ADULTS MIXED SEX PRESENT4 WITH CHILDREN PRESENT5 WITH ADULTS MIXED SEX AND CHILDREN PRESENT6				
G1.03. SEX OF RESPONDENT:	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">MALE.....1</td> <td style="width: 50%;">.....2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FEMALE.....1</td> <td>.....2</td> </tr> </table>	MALE.....12	FEMALE.....12				
MALE.....12								
FEMALE.....12								
G1.04 TYPE OF HOUSEHOLD	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; height: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">MALE AND FEMALE ADULT1</td> <td style="width: 50%;">.....2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FEMALE ADULT ONLY1</td> <td>.....2</td> </tr> </table>	MALE AND FEMALE ADULT12	FEMALE ADULT ONLY12				
MALE AND FEMALE ADULT12								
FEMALE ADULT ONLY12								

MODULE G2: ROLE IN HOUSEHOLD DECISION-MAKING AROUND PRODUCTION AND INCOME GENERATION

HOUSEHOLD IDENTIFICATION (IN DATA FILE, EACH SUB-MODULE (G2-G6) MUST BE LINKED WITH HH AND RESPONDENT ID

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RESPONDENT ID CODE

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ACTIVITY CODE	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	G2.01	G2.02	G2.03	G2.04	G2.05
	“Now I’d like to ask you some questions about your participation in certain types of work activities and on making decisions on various aspects of household life”	Did you yourself participate in [ACTIVITY] in the past 12 months (that is, during the last [one/two] cropping seasons), from [PRESENT MONTH] last year to [PRESENT MONTH] this year?	When decisions are made regarding [ACTIVITY], who is it that normally takes the decision? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE IF THE RESPONSE IS SELF ONLY SKIP TO QUESTION G2.05	How much input did you have in making decisions about [ACTIVITY]? USE DECISION CODES FOR G2.03/G2.05; IF NO DECISION MADE, ENTER 98 AND MOVE TO THE NEXT ACTIVITY	To what extent do you feel you can make your own personal decisions regarding [ACTIVITY] if you want(ed) to? CIRCLE ONE	How much input did you have in decisions on the use of income generated from [ACTIVITY] USE CODES FOR G2.03/G2.05
A	Food crop farming: These are crops that are grown primarily for household food consumption	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY B	SELF 1 SPOUSE 2 OTHER HH MEMBER 3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER 4 NOT APPLICABLE 98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL 1 SMALL EXTENT 2 MEDIUM EXTENT 3 TO A HIGH EXTENT .. 4	
B	Cash crop farming: These are crops that are grown primarily for sale in the market	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY C	SELF 1 SPOUSE 2 OTHER HH MEMBER 3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER 4 NOT APPLICABLE 98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL 1 SMALL EXTENT 2 MEDIUM EXTENT 3 TO A HIGH EXTENT .. 4	
C	Livestock raising	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY D	SELF 1 SPOUSE 2 OTHER HH MEMBER 3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER 4 NOT APPLICABLE 98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL 1 SMALL EXTENT 2 MEDIUM EXTENT 3 TO A HIGH EXTENT .. 4	
D	Non-farm economic activities: This would include things like running a small business, self-employment, buy-and-sell	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY E	SELF 1 SPOUSE 2 OTHER HH MEMBER 3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER 4 NOT APPLICABLE 98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL 1 SMALL EXTENT 2 MEDIUM EXTENT 3 TO A HIGH EXTENT .. 4	

G2.03/G2.05 DECISION CODES:
 NO INPUT OR INPUT IN FEW DECISIONS 01
 INPUT INTO SOME DECISIONS 02
 INPUT INTO MOST OR ALL DECISIONS 03
 NO DECISION MADE 98

ACTIVITY CODE	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	Did you yourself participate in [ACTIVITY] in the past 12 months (that is, during the last [one/two] cropping seasons), from [PRESENT MONTH] last year to [PRESENT MONTH] this year?	When decisions are made regarding [ACTIVITY], who is it that normally takes the decision? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE; IF THE RESPONSE IS SELF ONLY SKIP TO QUESTION G2.05	How much input did you have in making decisions about [ACTIVITY]? USE DECISION CODES FOR G2.03/G2.05 IF NO DECISION MADE, ENTER 98	To what extent do you feel you can make your own personal decisions regarding [ACTIVITY] if you want(ed) to? CIRCLE ONE	How much input did you have in decisions on the use of income generated from [ACTIVITY] USE CODES FOR G2.03/G2.05
		G2.01	G2.02	G2.03	G2.04	G2.05
E	Wage and salary employment: This could be work that is paid for in cash or in-kind, including both agriculture and other wage work	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY F	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL1 SMALL EXTENT2 MEDIUM EXTENT3 TO A HIGH EXTENT ...4	
F	Fishing or fishpond culture	YES 1 NO 2 → ACTIVITY G	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL1 SMALL EXTENT2 MEDIUM EXTENT3 TO A HIGH EXTENT ...4	
G	Major household expenditures (such as a bicycles, land, boda boda)		SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98 → NEXT ACTIVITY		NOT AT ALL1 SMALL EXTENT2 MEDIUM EXTENT3 TO A HIGH EXTENT ...4	
H	Minor household expenditures (such as food for daily consumption or other household needs)		SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98 → MODULE G3(A)		NOT AT ALL1 SMALL EXTENT2 MEDIUM EXTENT3 TO A HIGH EXTENT ...4	

G2.03/G2.05 DECISION CODES:
 NO INPUT OR INPUT IN FEW DECISIONS.....01
 INPUT INTO SOME DECISIONS.....02
 INPUT INTO MOST OR ALL DECISIONS.....03
 NO DECISION MADE98

MODULE G3(A): ACCESS TO PRODUCTIVE CAPITAL

"Now I'd like to ask you about your household's access to and ownership of a number of items that could be used to generate income."	Does anyone in your household currently have any [ITEM]?	Do you own any of the item? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
PRODUCTIVE CAPITAL¹	G3.01	G3.02
A Agricultural land (pieces/plots)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM B	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
B Large livestock (oxen, cattle)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM C	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
C Small livestock (goats, pigs, sheep)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM D	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
D Chickens, Ducks, Turkeys, Pigeons	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM E	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
E Fish pond or fishing equipment	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM F	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
F Farm equipment (non-mechanized: hand tools, animal-drawn plough)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM G	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
G Farm equipment (mechanized: tractor-plough, power tiller, treadle pump)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM H	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
H Nonfarm business equipment (solar panels used for recharging, sewing machine, brewing equipment, fryers)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM I	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
I House or other structures	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM J	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3

"Now I'd like to ask you about your household's access to and ownership of a number of items that could be used to generate income."	Does anyone in your household currently have any [ITEM]?	Do you own any of the item? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
PRODUCTIVE CAPITAL¹	G3.01	G3.02
J Large consumer durables (refrigerator, TV, sofa)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM K	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
K Small consumer durables (radio, cookware)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM L	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
L Cell phone	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM M	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
M Other land not used for agricultural purposes (pieces/plots, residential or commercial land)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → ITEM N	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3
N Means of transportation (bicycle, motorcycle, car)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → MODULE G3(B)	YES, SOLELY.....1 YES, JOINTLY.....2 NO.....3

¹ Examples given within productive capital categories are not extensive and should be adapted to local context by either adding to or replacing suggestions in parentheses.

MODULE G3(B): ACCESS TO CREDIT

LENDING SOURCE NAMES ²		G3.03	G3.04	G3.05	G3.06
<p>"Next I'd like to ask about your household's experience with borrowing money or other items in the past 12 months."</p>					
<p>Would you or anyone in your household be able to take a loan or borrow cash/in-kind from [SOURCE] if you wanted to? *</p>					
A	Non-governmental organization (NGO)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
B	Formal lender (bank/financial institution)	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
C	Informal lender	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
D	Friends or relatives	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
E	Group based micro-finance or lending including VSLAs / SACCOs	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE
F	Informal credit/savings groups such as merry-go-rounds, tontines, funeral societies, etc.	YES.....1 NO.....2 → NEXT SOURCE MAYBE.....3	YES, CASH.....1 YES, IN-KIND.....2 YES, CASH AND IN-KIND.....3 NO.....4 → NEXT SOURCE DON'T KNOW.....97]	SELF.....1 SPOUSE.....2 OTHER HH MEMBER.....3 OTHER NON-HH MEMBER.....4 NOT APPLICABLE.....98	Who makes the decision about what to do with the money/ item borrowed from [SOURCE] most of the time? CIRCLE ALL APPLICABLE

* This question is not included in the calculation of the index, but should be collected to be able to identify whether there is a credit constraint, for programming purposes

² To adapt to country context, locally relevant examples may be given within lending sources categories.

MODULE G4: TIME ALLOCATION

G4.01: PLEASE RECORD A LOG OF THE ACTIVITIES FOR THE INDIVIDUAL IN THE LAST COMPLETE 24 HOURS (STARTING YESTERDAY MORNING AT 4 AM, FINISHING 3:59 AM OF THE CURRENT DAY). THE TIME INTERVALS ARE MARKED IN 15 MIN INTERVALS AND ONE ACTIVITY CAN BE MARKED FOR EACH TIME PERIOD BY DRAWING A LINE THROUGH THAT ACTIVITY.

"Now I'd like to ask you about how you spent your time during the past 24 hours. We'll begin from yesterday morning, and continue through to this morning. This will be a detailed accounting. I'm interested in everything you do (i.e. resting, eating, personal care, work inside and outside the home, caring for children, cooking, shopping, socializing, etc.), even if it doesn't take you much time."

Activity	Night			Morning			Day								
	4	5	6	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15		
A Sleeping and resting															
B Eating and drinking															
C Personal care															
D School (also homework)															
E Work as employed															
F Own business work															
G Farming/livestock/fishing															
J Shopping/getting service (incl health services)															
K Weaving, sewing, textile care															
L Cooking															
M Domestic work (incl fetching wood and water)															
N Care for children/adults/elderly															
P Travelling and commuting															
Q Watching TV/listening to radio/reading															
T Exercising															
U Social activities and hobbies															
W Religious activities															
X Other, specify ...															

MODULE G4 continued: TIME ALLOCATION

Activity	Evening							Night						
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	1	2	3		
A														
B														
C														
D														
E														
F														
G														
J														
K														
L														
M														
N														
P														
Q														
T														
U														
W														
X														

QNO.	QUESTION	RESPONSE
G4.02	In the last 24 hours did you work (at home or outside of the home) more than usual, about the same as usual, or less than usual?	MORE THAN USUAL.....1 ABOUT THE SAME AS USUAL.....2 LESS THAN USUAL.....3

MODULE G5: GROUP MEMBERSHIP

"Now I'm going to ask you about groups in the community. These can be either formal or informal and customary groups."		Are you an active member of this [GROUP]?
GROUP CATEGORIES		G5.02
		G5.01
A	Agricultural / livestock/ fisheries producer's group (including marketing groups)	YES1 NO2 → GROUP B DON'T KNOW97
B	Water users' group	YES1 NO2 → GROUP C DON'T KNOW97
C	Forest users' group	YES1 NO2 → GROUP D DON'T KNOW97
D	Credit or microfinance group (including SACCOs/merry-go-rounds/ VSLAs)	YES1 NO2 → GROUP E DON'T KNOW97
E	Mutual help or insurance group (including burial societies)	YES1 NO2 → GROUP F DON'T KNOW97
F	Trade and business association group	YES1 NO2 → GROUP G DON'T KNOW97
G	Civic groups (improving community) or charitable group (helping others)	YES1 NO2 → GROUP H DON'T KNOW97
H	Religious group	YES1 NO2 → GROUP J DON'T KNOW97
I	Other [women's/men's] group (only if it does not fit into one of the other categories)	YES1 NO2 → GROUP K DON'T KNOW97
J	Other (SPECIFY) _____	YES1 NO2 DON'T KNOW97

END OF QUESTIONNAIRE. FILL OUT COVER PAGE OUTCOME G1.05.

